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**ABSTRACT
BOOK**

PP186. Anti-cholestatic activity of bile acids mediated by glutathione-dependent antioxidant system

Pavlovic N¹, Stanimirov B¹, Djanić M¹, Mikov M¹, Stankov K¹

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Medicine, Novi Sad, Serbia

Introduction: Ursodeoxycholic acid (UDCA) is widely used agent for the treatment of cholestatic liver disorders, while its epimer, chenodeoxycholic acid (CDCA), as hydrophobic compound may exert toxic effects, but can also activate the farnesoid X receptor (FXR). FXR is the main regulator of bile acid homeostasis and the development of FXR ligands represents a new approach for the treatment of cholestasis. The aim of our study was to determine the effects of low, non-toxic doses of CDCA on parameters of oxidative stress in cholestatic rats.

Methods: Rats with intrahepatic cholestasis induced by 17 α -ethynylestradiol (EE) were treated with 10 mg/kg of CDCA and 25 mg/kg of UDCA during 5 days. Gene expression analysis was performed by SybrGreen-based qRT-PCR assay and activities of glutathione-peroxidase (GPx) and glutathione-reductase (GR) were measured using kinetic spectrophotometric methods. The study was approved by the Ethical Committee of the University of Novi Sad.

Results: The induction of cholestatic damage by EE was associated with 5-fold and 2-fold increase of expression of GPx and GR genes, respectively. Activities of these enzymes were also significantly increased in the livers of EE-treated rats ($p < 0.05$). Both CDCA and UDCA decreased expression of GPx gene 2-fold. GR expression was also significantly reduced by CDCA treatment ($p < 0.05$), while UDCA did not have that effect. Treatment with bile acids exerted similar effects on activities of studied antioxidant enzymes, but UDCA was shown to be more effective than CDCA in reducing both GPx and GR activities, suggesting the involvement of post-translational modifications of these proteins induced by CDCA and UDCA.

Conclusions: Both UDCA and CDCA exhibit protection against estradiol-induced oxidative liver damage and cholestasis through modulation of glutathione-dependent pathways.

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